

County Center for Educational Resources and Assistance, Argeș
Centrul Județean de Resurse și Asistență Educațională Argeș

AsProEdu Association

Asociația AsProEdu

Synthezis, Noventa Padovana, Italy

Personal Development International Conference

2nd Edition - Pitești 2022

Book of abstracts

Editura Ars Libri

County Center for Educational Resources and Assistance, Argeş
Centrul Judeţean de Resurse şi Asistenţă Educaţională Argeş

AsProEdu Association

Asociaţia AsProEdu

Synthezis, Noventa Padovana, Italy

**Personal Development
International Conference
2nd Edition - Piteşti 2022**

Book of abstracts

Ars Libri

Edition coordinators:

Mihaela Lungu

Rodica Emilia Ciucă

Cristina Ipate-Toma

Book of abstracts (Personal Development International Conference)

ISSN 2821 – 6474

ISSN-L 2821 – 6474

The authors of the articles assume responsibility for their originality.

Reviewed by

Costin Marian Crînguș

Universitatea Lucian Blaga din Sibiu, România

costin_cringus@yahoo.co.uk

Cristiana Crețu

Inspectoratul Școlar Județean Argeș, România

cristianacretu2005@yahoo.com

Elena Lucreția Neacșu

Colegiul Național „Al. Odobescu” Pitești, România

lucyneacsu79@yahoo.com

Ana-Maria Badea

CJRAE Argeș, România

psi.amaria@gmail.com

Silvia Bragagnolo

Synthesis srl, Italy

progettazione@synthesis-srl.com

Plenary Opening

Moderator: Mihaela Lungu

Translator: Camelia Ioanăș

Special Guests:

Antoneta - Georgina BOLCHIȘ – State Secretary - Romanian Ministry of Education

Dumitru TUDOSOIU – General Inspector of Argeș County School Inspectorate

Adrian BUGHIU – Vicepresident of County Council Argeș

Cristina MARIN – Inspector in the Romanian Ministry of Education

Prof. Dr. Maria CONSTANTINESCU – Pitești University

Costin DEDU – President of Imago Mundi Association

Hosts:

Ciucă Emilia Rodica – Headmaster of County Center for Educational Resources and Assistance, Argeș

Ruse Cătălin – President of AsProEdu Association

Section A

"Psychology and Development"

Session 1

"Psychology and development" – PPS

Moderator: Mihaela Lungu

SENSE OF BELONGING: A PATH TO DEVELOPMENT

(1) Herculano ANDRADE

(1) Master' degree in Psychology, Portugal

The search for the sense of belonging seems to be something inherent to the human being. In fact, Aristotle already defended that man is a social subject that, by nature, needs to belong to a collectivity. As such, we are always looking to be part of something, and this search is reflected in the relationships we establish. Let's look at the need we have to meet people and belong to a group of friends.

Being part of something makes us feel more special and, therefore, the search for belonging is seen not only in personal relationships, but in other parts of life, such as choosing a job that can offer this feeling.

When in the school or professional context, the sense of belonging transforms relationships, dedication and the results achieved, whoever experiences a greater sense of belonging, expects more results. The sense of belonging is an essential part of the knowledge construction process. It encourages the creation of a safe space for creative exploration and the development of individual critical thinking.

Even in the last century, Zygmunt Bauman alerted us to the concept of liquid modernity, which presupposes those social relations, among others, are fragile, fleeting and malleable, like liquids – the opposite of the sense of belonging. Thus, the current challenge is the (re)construction of this feeling, which allows the full construction of the Safe Self and with critical thinking.

Keywords: sense of belonging; creativity; development; critical thinking; construction.

Socialization of children with special educational needs

- (1) Aurelia Mihaela DĂNEASA
- (2) Liviu MOISE
- (3) Atena Luminița ILIE
- (4) Florentina CIULEI

- (1) Centru Școlar de Educație Incluzivă „Aurora” Reșița, România
mihdan22@yahoo.com
- (2) Centrul Județean de Resurse și Asistență Educațională, Caraș Severin, România
liviumoise68@yahoo.com
- (3) Drd. UPS Chișinău, Școala Gimnazială Petrești, Dâmbovița
ilieatenaluminita@yahoo.com
- (4) Drd. UPSC Chișinău, GPP Rază de soare, Târgoviște, Dâmbovița
ciuleiflorentina81@gmail.com

Objectives: The purpose of the research is to highlight the effectiveness of the intervention through psycho-pedagogical therapy and support program, in the education and training of students with special educational needs integrated in the public mainstream school, as an inclusive school, in order to increase the degree of socialization in the group of students.

Material and methods: Observation - observation grid, School purchase samples, Sentence completion test, sociometric test, Investigation based on interview

Results: The processing of the sociometric test data shows better overall scores compared to the scores from the initial assessment, with students benefiting from more choices from peers and fewer rejections. Comparing the status indices obtained at the initial assessment with those obtained at the final assessment, we can see that, although they mostly remain negative, they have increased in absolute value, demonstrating the effectiveness of the counseling and group therapy that the subjects benefited from. The results and scores obtained lead to the conclusion that the degree of inclusion and the expansion of subjects in the group have increased considerably.

The observation data showed an important decrease in the manifestations of hyperactivity and lack of attention, the students being much more orderly and more responsive to the requests of the teaching staff in the class. Also, a better collaboration with colleagues was found during the activities.

Conclusions: The final conclusion that emerges from the research carried out is that the socialization of children with special educational needs integrated in mainstream school can be achieved successfully if they benefit from specialized support services and individualized intervention programs for recovery, compensation and amelioration of disorders and which to lead to the normalization of their lives in an appropriate social framework.

Keywords: Education, Therapies, Socialization.

SELF EFFICACY, WELLBEING AND INITIATIVE FOR PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT AT TEACHERS

(1) Robert-Florin MINCULESCU

(1) Center for Educational Resources and Assistance, Argeş County, Romania
+40732.993.336, robertminculescu@yahoo.com

The objective of the research is the study of the relationship between self-efficacy, wellbeing and the initiative for personal development in teachers.

Materials and Methods: Inference statistics. Hypothesis 1 - In order to examine the association between the self-efficacy dimension and the dimensions associated with personal well-being we chose the Pearson correlation as a statistical procedure. Hypothesis 2 - In order to examine the association between the dimensions associated with personal wellbeing and the dimension of initiative for development, we chose spearman test as a statistical procedure. Hypothesis 3 - In order to examine the association between the self-efficacy dimension and the personal Development Initiative dimension, we chose the Spearman test as a statistical procedure.

Results: Hypothesis 1 stated that teachers with a high level of self-efficacy will also report a high level of personal well-being and we could not confirm hypothesis number 1. Hypothesis 2 was not confirmed by the study. Hypothesis 3 stated that teachers with a high level of self-efficacy will also report a high level of personal development initiative. Based on the results obtained it was not confirmed hypothesis 3.

Conclusion: One of the reasons why the 3 hypotheses have not been confirmed can also be due to the conditions in which the teachers operate. The nature of the environment, often does not provide enough benefits to give a teacher the peace or the sense of security.

Keywords: Efficacy, Wellbeing, Personal, Development, Teach.

COMMUNICATION, AN ESSENTIAL COMPONENT IN EDUCATIONAL CONFLICT MANAGEMENT

- (1) Harun ULUCAN,
- (2) Atena Luminița ILIE,
- (3) Alexandru George ȚICĂU,
- (4) Tefrik YILDIRIM,
- (5) Seda Şeker YILMAZ

- (1) Mehmet Akif Ersoy İlkokulu, Emirgazi, Turkye hulukan42@gmail.com
- (2) Școala Gimnazială Petrești, jud. Dâmbovița, doctorand UPS "Ion Creangă"- Chișinău, ilieatenaluminita@yahoo.com
- (3) Școala Gimnazială de Arte „N. N. Tonitza”, Bârlad, jud. Vaslui, doctorand UPS "Ion Creangă" -Chișinău, alexticau@yahoo.com
- (4) Kepsut İlçe Milli Eğitim Müdürü, Turkye
- (5) Sincan İnci Anaokulu, Turkye

Objectives: The study of conflict management is increasingly approached in human resource management because it contributes to a better understanding of individual and group behaviors within an organization. In general, conflict appears as a form of human interaction through which two or more members of a community disagree in whole or in part on issues.

In other words, conflict is the intentional interference of an individual or group in the efforts to achieve the goals of another group. Because the goals of the two parties are often incompatible, the achievement of the goal by one party makes it impossible for the other party to achieve it.

Results: The study of conflict management is increasingly addressed in human resources management because it contributes to a better knowledge of individual and group behaviors within an organization. In general, conflict appears as a form of human interaction through which two or more members of a community enter into total or partial disagreement on some issues. In other words, conflict is the intentional interference of an individual or a group in the efforts to achieve the goals of another group. Since the goals of the two parties are often incompatible, the achievement of the goal by one of the parties makes it impossible for the other party to achieve it. Conflict is a natural component of our everyday existence, of our relationships with others; therefore, most of the time we don't even think about it and we don't study it; if we stop looking at it as a negative, destructive force, but try to explain its nature and identify the causes and forces involved, the conflict can become a chance for maturation. The development of certain specific skills, both for solving conflicts, but especially for dealing with them, leads to students being responsible for their actions, to awareness of the consequences of their actions. The ability to approach conflicts in a constructive way contributes to mental and individual health and has positive effects on society in general.

Conclusions: Preventing and resolving conflicts in school is a priority that requires concrete measures, in partnership, involving the following factors: schools, protection and assistance services, the police, the church, the media, the family, society as a whole. The school must prepare the future adult so that he can prevent the conflicts he faces and avoid them when necessary or at least solve them in the best way, so that both he and those involved are not stopped in this process of change and evolution and, therefore, of personal development.

Keywords: conflict, educational environment, educational conflict, conflict states, conflict management, negotiation.

Section B

“Education and Development”

Session 1

”Pedagogy of art and innovation” - PPS

Moderator: Camelia Ioanăș

**AN EVIDENCE-BASED INTERVENTION TO PROMOTE STUDENT
ENGAGEMENT AND PREVENT LATER PSYCHOLOGICAL DIFFICULTIES: THE
GOOD BEHAVIOR GAME**

**(1)(2)Flora LORENZO,
(2)Laércia VASCONCELOS,
(1)Ingunn SANDAKER,
(2)Marília PACHECO**

(1) OsloMet – Oslo Metropolitan University, Department of Behavioral Sciences, Oslo, Norway

(2) University of Brasília – UnB, Department of Basic Psychological Processes, Brasília, Brazil

Address correspondence to: Flora Lorenzo, Stensberggata 26, 0170 Oslo, Phone +47 96804059, E-mail: floralor@oslomet.no

Objectives. The purpose of this paper is to inform practitioners and policymakers from the Education sector about an intervention with consistent results concerning the promotion of pupil engagement in academic activities, as well as on reducing child exposure to risk factors linked to substance abuse and other psychological difficulties at adulthood. With consistent replications of its positive results, the Good Behavior Game favors the prevalence of nurturing practices, cooperation, and positive socialization in primary schools, being one of the most cost-effective universal school-based programs in the prevention field. The objectives comprise presenting: (a) one analysis of accidental strengthening of disruptions and distractions in classroom settings, (b) an overview of the program effects, including those from a culturally adapted version to Brazil, and (c) a culturo-behavior design of pathways to increase the program sustainability.

Material and methods. Whereas variables described in the operant selection literature served as conceptual tools for performing a functional analysis of disruption in schools, variables described in the culturo-behavior literature guided the design of metacontingencies to enhance the program sustainability through local autonomy. Furthermore, in addition to presenting an overview of the literature concerning the Good Behavior Game effects, a multiple baseline experimental design across five classrooms from two municipalities was used to evaluate whether a culturally adapted version to Brazil replicated the program's consistent positive effects.

Results. Concerning the efficacy study, results showed a systematic increase in on-task behavior and a systematic decrease in distractions and disruptive behaviors among pupils, which replicate the effects reported in the international literature, in particular via single-case experimental designs.

Conclusions. Together, the analyses and the data comprised in this work highlight the availability of one evidence-based and cost-effective intervention to promote positive impacts in schools and protect pupils from vulnerable developmental spirals linked to future negative mental health outcomes.

Keywords: Good Behavior Game, On-task behavior, Academic engagement, Prevention.

THE THEATER PEDAGOGY: THE EDUCATION THROUGH PLAY AND CREATIVITY

(1) Larisa TRĂISTARU

(1) National University of San Juan, Argentina

As the theatre represents a synthesis of the popular arts, its grandiose periods are linked to the periods and events of each culture and they are being products of the social conditions and of the predominant cultural aspects, that is to say the reflection of those cultures.

We call reflection not only that which is shown mimetically, but also, and above all, that which society hides and does not allow talking about it, despite being present in the collective imagination. These reflections find their place in the theatre, usually through the magic of metaphors. Since it is a living art, the theatre represents one of the strongest political instruments, which impacts and challenges people not only at a cognitive level, but also emotionally, and has the ability to arouse ideas, modify thoughts, or even change people's ways of being. Based on emotions, the theatre requires a procedural, internal work, so that people we work with can open up. And here comes the pedagogical responsibility of a drama teacher: in this dangerous game where apparently there are no rules, but only role-playing games, characters, and plenty of possibilities of directing other people's bodies and souls, there is actually a fundamental rule to take into account - the pedagogy.

From the academic spaces of acting training and theatrical research of which I took part of in the last three years, at the National University of San Juan, an attempt has been made to generate creative and critical thinking about acting, about theatre, and mainly about pedagogy, as the students are getting prepared to be both artists and teachers. While spaces for artistic and pedagogical experimentation and creation are proposed in the chair, action days and laboratories are proposed from the research project, in order to analyse the application of theoretical-practical methods in teaching spaces and to evaluate the pedagogical process.

Keywords: education, pedagogy, theatre, acting.

Session 2

”Professionals in schools” – PPS

Moderator: Mihaela LUNGU

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF EDUCATIONAL ADJUSTMENT BETWEEN INDIA AND ROMANIA CHILDREN

(1) Ronakkumar Rajubhai PARMAR

(2) Atena Luminita ILIE

(1) Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology, Children's University, Gandhinagar

(2) Scola Gimnaziala Petresti, doctorand UPS Ion Creanga-Chisinau

Objectives: Adjustment is a lifelong and continue process. The prime aim of the present study is to identify and compare educational adjustment between Indian and Romanian Children. The main focus of the study was to compare the educational adjustment in Indian boys compared to Romanian boys, Indian girls compared to Romanian girls pursuing secondary school and we also compared the school adjustment in urban vs rural areas of India and Romania.

Materials and methods: We used the method of sampling, choosing a number of 30 boys and 30 girls from both countries from urban and rural areas. All this information was collected through Google forms using the Educational Adjustment Inventory.

Results: The interpretation of the results indicated there was significant main difference between relations to their gender and rural area, but the urban area of each country was insignificant regarding the educational adjustment.

Conclusions: Secondary school pupils in both Romania and India are going through the process of educational adjustment, regardless of age, sex or living area (rural or urban), however there are not many differences in the urban area when comparing Indian pupils to Romanian pupils.

Keywords: Education, Adjustment, Secondary School.

INTERCULTURAL EDUCATION

- (1) Atena Luminița ILIE
- (2) Serkan MUSTAFA
- (3) Hassan RAZA
- (4) Tülin KARAĞAÇ

(1) Școala Gimnazială Petrești, jud. Dâmbovița, Drd. UPS "Ion Creangă"-Chișinău
ilieatenaluminita@yahoo.com

(2) MEHMET AKIF ERSOY ILKOKULU, Emirgazi/Konya, TURKIYE,
s.m.akyol@hotmail.com

(3) University of Gujrat, Gujrat, hassanguijjar007raza@gmail.com

(4) Kağıthane Atatürk İlkokulu, Turkye

Objectives: Intercultural education is now become a integral part of the new era. Without this you cannot interact with different culture ,linguistic and behavioral people.it enhancing the efficiency of intercultural relation, increasing tolerance and acceptance towards those who are different. In short it is the only key which can reduce linguistics, religious and cultural barriers and encourage us to understand each other with patience and spread positivity

Results: The word is becoming more and more interconnected and people from vastly different context and background now come into contact on regular bases weather at university in their work or in OTHER everyday situation.

Due to this modern technology, world became a global village, we have easy access to every part of the world in no time and because of this, the issue of cohabitation together is increasingly approached in the modern society. We all are belonging to different linguistic, religious, and behavioral backgrounds and we faced a lot of hurdles during interactions. So intercultural education is the only process to overcome these hurdles. Many of us go abroad for jobs, for studies, for research, for tourism due to cultural differences gap left which can only be filled by intercultural education. learning the intercultural education is mandatory in recent era because everyone have its own thoughts, its own culture, own way of seeing the word and own religious beliefs so we must respect them and treat with the people according to their taste so we can develop a peaceful globe. It is the new type of education which focus on all these aspects and promote positivity

Conclusions: Interculture education is the most important factor which can deal the conflicts between different people having different thought, which is not easy to resolve. It teaches us to respect the religion and culture of other which create a good environment for better world. So, we should have to learn the interculture education so that we may achieve these goals.

Keywords: integral, intercultural education, linguistics, reflective observation, conflict management, cohabitation.

SCHOOL-FAMILY COOPERATION AND COMMUNICAITON WITH PARENTS

(1) Fevzi ENES

(2) Harun Mehmet ULUCAN

(1) Aydođan Emrulgazi Secondary School, Emirgazi, Graduate Student in NEU in Konya
fevenes@hotmail.com

(2) Akif Ersoy Elementary School, Emirgazi, Graduate Student in NEU in Konya
hulucan42@gmail.com

Objectives: The educational process of students helps to adapt to the environment and society in which they live. It also enables the development and transfer of cultural values to new generations. The basis of the educational process is based on learning. The learning process of the child begins in the family with the birth and it continues with school, which is a planned and programmed institution. This essay was written to state the purpose and importance of the school-parent union which should be established at school in order to provide quality education to children and to emphasize how to communicate with parents who are natural members of this union.

Results: Today, the fact that school-family relations remain only at an economic level makes it difficult for families to participate in school. Therefore, families cannot meet with teachers and administrators about the issues they lack and the problems they encounter. For this reason, families are either unaware of the problems they encounter with their children's learning situations, or they do not know how to solve these problems even if they are aware of them. The main causes of parents' indifference towards school are negative attitudes of teachers, child's failure, not getting any results, schools that asking for money, teachers giving advice, having a formal atmosphere in schools, insufficient communication with the school, lack of time for parents, lots of their own work.

Conclusions: It is difficult to say that the teacher or the school alone is sufficient in the education of the child. For this reason, the support of families, which is an integral part of education, is needed. School-family cooperation has various benefits for all stakeholders of the school. It can be said that one of the most important benefits of this cooperation is to positively affect students' success and psychology. There are some changes that can be done in school environment to develop school – family relationships. For example, using positive language, making parents feel valued, informing the parents well about the work done at school.

Keywords: relationship, parent, school, partnership

NON FORMAL EDUCATION FOR ENGLISH TEACHING

- (1) George Vasile Ilie,
- (2) Rodica Ilie,
- (3) Florina Laura Tirlescu,
- (4) Elisabeta Veluta Dumitru

(1) Liceul Tehnologic Auto Cămpulung, email adress: georgesileilie@yahoo.com
(2) (3) (4) Argeş County center for Resources and Educational Resources.

Objectives: The objectives of this paper are to familiarize the audience with the four pillars of education: learning to be, learning to do, learning to know and learning to live together.

Materials and methods: qualitative literature research on the non-formal education topic. The methods and the theories that non formal education make a good response are the four piles of support named by UNESCO "The Treasure Within". In our project, we make reference of those four piles which respond to our objectives, visions, values and experiences.

Results: Non formal learning helps individuals with decision - making and builds self – confidence. For example in helping street children, this type of education is a lifelong process of learning and sharing knowledge and skills.

Conclusion: Non formal education (NFE) is an organized activity which takes sort outside the school system. It is flexible in generally, student centered. It presents several advantages and disadvantages, but we encourage teachers to use some of its techniques to make learning more appealing to students, as it has been proven to increase learning interest for pupils of all ages.

Key words: non-formal education, pupil centered

DEVELOPING COMPETENCES IN SCIENCE TEACHING PROCESS

(1) Mariana Ghiță,
(2) Mădălina Ghiță,
(3) Luiza Maria Ana

(1) (2) (3) Argeș County Center for Educational Resources and Assistance,
ghitamariana79@yahoo.com

Objectives: The main objective of this paper is to bring a new perspective on the science teaching in formal, non-formal and informal methods of teaching. These methods are prone to develop in students civic and social skills, initiative and entrepreneurship.

Materials and methods: Qualitative and quantitative literature research were used for this paper.

Results: Digitalization of the science teaching process was shown to increase certain life abilities for students and also encouraged lifelong learning.

Conclusion: Interdisciplinarity and transdisciplinary are now encouraged as part of modern teaching. For example, during biology classes students are also learning mathematical skills and also, they are using computer assisted lessons, enhancing their digital skills.

Key words: lifelong learning, interdisciplinarity, transdisciplinarity.

Section C
"Non-refundable Projects"

Session 1

”Non-refundable grants opportunities” - PPS

Moderator: Ana-Maria Badea

CHILDREN'S RIGHTS, AWARENESS AND PARTICIPATION IN TIMES OF CRISIS. HOW CAN NGO'S AND SCHOOLS WORK TOGETHER FOR SUPPORTING CHILDREN AND YOUTH?

(1) Constantin Dedu

(1) Imago Mundi Association, Argeş, Romania

Title: CL.A.P. – ChiLdren's rights Awareness and Participation addressing emerging needs in Covid-19 pandemic project.

Objective: to contribute to increase the fulfilment and the awareness on the rights of the child, through actions that put forward the EU Strategy on the rights of the child and enhancing the children's participation in identifying needs and overcome the impact of the pandemic on children.

Funding: Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values Programme (CERV), total budget awarded for the project, 147 469.96 Euro.

Coordinator and Partners: coordinated by CISS ONG Italy, and has partners from Romania - Imago Mundi and Asociația Replika, Spain - AHEAD, and ICDI from the Netherlands, and unfolds between May 2022 and May 2024.

Management, activities: Children's participation in COVID-19 related decision making has been limited. By promoting the engagement of children in decision making process and raise the awareness on children's rights, the project supports the active role of children as political subjects, promoting their involvement in overcoming the impact of the pandemic. The project is articulated in 4 interconnected work packages which aim to: establish transnational partnerships committed in protect and promote the children's rights and participation; develop a need assesment process using creative methods, taking gender-specific aspects into account; build the capacities of the educators in children-addressed services based in Italy, Romania, Spain; increase the children's opportunities to take part to the decision making process, guaranteeing the launch of a mechanism of children's consultations by local public authorities.

Results of the Action: a protocol for children's consultation mechanism is signed by the local public authorities; 435 children (50% girls) are involved in the Action; 210 educators in child-related services, 30 children-addressed services, 30 local institutions and public bodies representatives are reached. The final public events involve 300 people in total.

Key words: children s rights, after-pandemic, education.

ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVES OF ARGEȘ COUNTY THROUGH ACCORDING TO THE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY IN THE 2021-2027 PROGRAMMING PERIOD

(1) Dr. Cristina Voicu Olteanu

(1) Arges County Council, Square Vasile Milea, România, voltercristina1980@gmail.com

Title of the project: Implementation of measures and tools aimed to improve administrative processes within the Arges County Council

Coordinator of the project: Management Authority for Administrative Capacity Operational Program 2014-2020

Source of the Grant: Argeș County Territorial Administrative Unit

Objectives: The general objective of the project consists in improving institutional strategic planning and simplifying the procedures implemented at the level of the Argeș County Council

Management details: the total value of the financing contract is 2,943,139.02 RON, of which:
- the total non-refundable amount requested is 2,884,276.24 RON
- the beneficiary's contribution is 58,862.78 RON.

Implementation period: 39 months

Activities approved: creation of electronic archive of documents, IT solution for managing the electronic archive, Sustainable Development Strategy of Argeș County, staff trained in the field of strategic management and the use of the IT solution made in the project.

Results: 1 electronic archive 1; IT solution; 1 Development Strategy, 40 people trained

Conclusions: institutional strategic planning was improved and the procedures implemented at the Argeș County Council level were simplified

Keywords: Archive, Solution, Strategy.

GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE ERASMUS+ PROGRAMME FOR 2021 - 2027

- (1) Atena Luminita ILIE
- (2) Ersan PARLAK
- (3) Haci Ismail KILIÇ

- (1) Școala Gimnazială Petrești, doctorand UPS "Ion Creangă"-Chișinău, ilieatenaluminita@yahoo.com
- (2) Ünye İlçe Milli Eğitim Müdürlüğü Ünye/Ordu TÜRKYE, ersanparlak@gmail.com
- (3) High School YUNUS EMRE, OSMANYE, TURCIA, hacikilic80@hotmail.com

Objectives: Erasmus+ is the EU Programme in the fields of education, training, youth and sport for the period 2021-2027. Education, training, youth and sport are key areas that support citizens in their personal and professional development. The objectives of this papers consist in promoting developing digital skills and competences and skills in forward-looking fields, such as combating climate change, clean energy, artificial intelligence, robotics, big data analysis, which is essential for Europe's future sustainable growth and cohesion.

Materials and methods: for this paper we used qualitative literature research.

Results: Promoting Erasmus+ to the wide public in Dâmbovița County resulted in increasing the interest for non-refundable funds and also increased the number of applications for projects.

Conclusions: Since the 1st of January 2007, the moment from which Romania became part of the European Union, the country had an enormous chance of applying for non-refundable funds for decreasing poverty, increasing social inclusion and digitalisation. Every public information regarding this Erasmus+ funds is statistically leading to more funds absorbed by public or private organisations.

Keywords: education, funds, non-refundable.

TOGETHER FOR EDUCATION

(1) Antoneta TUDORACHE

(1) Mariuța Carmen CHIRIȚESCU

(1) Elena Simona COTESCU

(2) Andreea LUPU

(1) "Petre Tudose" Secondary School, Mălureni, Argeș , Romania

(2) CJRAE Arges, Arges, Romania

Address correspondence to Antoneta Tudorache (school principal), Mariuța Carmen Chirițescu, Elena Simona Cotescu: 128 Main Street, Mălureni, Argeș county, Romania

Address correspondence to Andreea Lupu, email address: deeea_mihaela@yahoo.com

Objectives: The project is part of the solution we propose in order to reduce and prevent early dropout of school among a considerable number of school students from our school whose economic and social situation is a precarious one. The main objectives are: reducing the rate of absenteeism and school dropout; preventing the risk of school dropout by integrating students from vulnerable groups in a harmonious, learning-friendly environment; prevention of early school drop-out; improving the situation in instruction and education and promoting the possibility by the participation of 92 students in a remedial education program; increasing the participation rate in EN and transition to the upper secondary cycle; implementation of extracurricular programs, non-formal activities designed to increase motivation for learning; strengthening and improving the student-parent-school relationship.

Materials and methods: counseling, questionnaires.

Results (expected): Decreasing in the abandonment rate compared to the reference year; improvement of school results due to remedial activities; increasing the completion rate of secondary education; development of social-emotional skills and teamwork for members of the vulnerable group; an active involvement of parents and the local community in the educational process; improving pedagogical competences and diversifying approaches in the teaching-learning-assessment process as a result of the use of modern technologies.

Conclusions: The completion of the project will not mean the cessation of activities or the lack of concern for the investments made both at the level of facilities and at the human level. We will continue to maintain and improve the active relationship and communication with students' families and local authorities, we will implement other projects to support our approach and we will certainly be in permanent partnership with members of the local community and other education providers.

Keywords: education, remedial studies, school dropout.

Session 2

„Projects and funds for development” - PPS

Moderator: Camelia Ioanăș

CREATING AND IMPLEMENTING INTEGRATED COMMUNITY SERVICES FOR FIGHTING POVERTY AND SOCIAL EXCLUSION

(1) Mihaela Pătru,

(2) Raluca Burcea

(1) CJRAE Argeş, Bd. Eroilor nr. 4-6, Piteşti, Argeş, email:

mihaelapatru1975@gmail.com

(2) „Dinu Lipatti” National College, Bucureşti, email: yayuta@yahoo.com

Objectives: the main objective of the project aims at increasing social inclusion and fighting poverty through developing integrated community services in 139 rural communities that are marginalized above average. People in this communities benefit from integrated social services, adapted to all their identified needs. The community team represents the local team, involved in providing integrated services, in Argeş County there are 5 teams.

Methods and materials: School counseling is the main method used for families/pupils counseling regarding schooling options; thematic courses at the community level; parent awareness activities regarding the importance of early education; informing the children's families, the young people in the community about the institutions they can turn to for the solution of various problems that affect the children/young people; updating the database of children at risk of dropping out of school and encouraging their participation in education.

Results: More than 70 people, students and parents were advised: regarding the importance of early education, 4 children being enrolled in kindergarten; 24 people were identified to benefit from the "Second chance" type program, 15 people will benefit from the training program in the commercial worker field; pupils at risk of dropping out were identified and counseled and encouraged to participate in education.

Conclusions: The project achieves a collaboration between equal partners, for common interests. The school-family-community partnership approaches children and their parents as interested participants and increases the chances that the beneficiaries of the project will in turn be responsible.

Keywords: project, education, counseling.

” DEVELOPING INCLUSION ÎN DIVERSITY - D.I.D.” 2021-1-RO01-KA122-ADU-000020313 – SUCCESFUL CLOSING PROJECT

(1)(2) Mihaela LUNGU
(1)(3) Elisabeta Veluța DUMITRU
(1)(4) Ana-Maria BADEA
(1)(5) Cătălin BOTAȘ

- (1) Centrul Județean de Resurse și Asistență Educațională, Argeș, Romania
- (2) Liceul Teoretic ”Ion Cantacuzino”, Pitești, Romania
- (3) Grădinița Specială Sfânta Elena, Pitești, Romania
- (4) Centrul Logopedic Interșcolar, Pitești, Romania
- (5) Liceul Tehnologic „Astra”, Pitești, Romania

Address correspondence to: Mihaela Lungu, CJRAE Argeș, B-dul. Eroilor. Nr. 4-6, Pitești, (Inspectoratul Școlar Județean) Argeș, Romania Ph./Fax.: +40 348730442; E-mail: mihaela.lungu@gmail.com

Program Operator: Agenția Națională pentru Programe Comunitare în Domeniul Educației și Formării Profesionale (ANPCDFP)[Romanian National Agency for Community Programs in the field of Education and Professional Training]

Project Promoter: Coordinator Centrul Județean de Resurse și Asistență Educațională, Argeș (CJRAE), Pitești, Romania. E10146916, www.cjrae-arges.ro

Source of the Grant: Erasmus+ Grants, KA122-ADU - Short-term projects for mobility of learner and staff in adult education (2021)

Partners: ASSOCIACAO INTERCULTURAL AMIGOS DA MOBILIDADE, Portugal Norte, BARCELOS. E10207576, www.mobilityfriends.org

Objectives: Dissemination is the purpose of this paper, regarding the activities evolution, and results of the project. The objectives are: Public dissemination of the evolution state of the project; Offering details about the activity aspects and the project management; Raising project education in the community (especially for participants interested to apply for grants).

Management details: Approved budget 31800 EURO. Time 12 months (1 December 2021 – 30 October 2022).

Activities approved. Counsellors and speech therapist training, Specific non-formal activities for teachers, Specific activities for parents, Intellectual products issuing.

Results. 10 teachers were trained regarding: Inclusion of the pupils with Special Education Requirements; Pupils subject of repatriation/ immigration; Adults curriculum design; Improved skills for communication with parents; Online training strategies. The training package for Romanian teachers is elaborated and waiting for ministerial improvement, after that it will be implemented for other 20 school counsellors.

Conclusions. The project is going as expected, and it will be finished on time. The capacities of CJRAE Argeș, are growing and it is planned to keep developing the skills of the personal and administration also.

Keywords: Education, Grants, Projects.

**”OPTIMIZED PUPIL TOOLS TO INCREASE SOCIAL INCLUSION AND ACCESS
ON THE LABOR MARKET - OptimaL” 2021-EY-PMIP-0002 – SUCCESSFUL
CLOSING PROJECT**

(1)(2) Mihaela LUNGU
(1) Emilia Rodica CIUCĂ
(1) Camelia IOANĂȘ

(1) Centrul Județean de Resurse și Asistență Educațională, Argeș, Romania
(2) Liceul Teoretic ”Ion Cantacuzino”, Pitești, Romania

Address correspondence to: Mihaela Lungu, CJRAE Argeș, B-dul. Eroilor. Nr. 4-6, Pitești, (Inspectoratul Școlar Județean) Argeș, Romania Ph./Fax.: +40 348730442; E-mail: mihaela.lungu@gmail.com

Program Operator: Agenția Națională pentru Programe Comunitare în Domeniul Educației și Formării Profesionale (ANPCDEFP)[Romanian National Agency for Community Programs in the field of Education and Professional Training]

Project Promoter: Coordinator Centrul Județean de Resurse și Asistență Educațională, Argeș (CJRAE), Pitești, Romania. E10146916, www.cjrae-arges.ro

Source of the Grant: EEA Grants 2014-2021, Education, Scholarship, Apprenticeship and Youth Entrepreneurship Programme in Romania (2021)

Partners: Newschool AS, Oslo, Norway. E10041764, <http://newschool.me>

Objectives: The goal this information, is to disseminate the activities evolution, and results of the project. The objectives are: To offer an image of the evolution faze of the project; Presenting details about the financial issues and project management; Raising project awareness in the community (especially for participants interested to apply for grants).

Management details: Approved budget 11473,69 EURO. Time 16 months (1 March 2022 – 30 June 2023).

Activities approved. Counsellor’s training, Specific non-formal activities for teachers, Specific activities for parents, Intellectual products issuing.

Results. 4 teachers were trained regarding: labour market research and prognosis, national and international educational resources investigation, streamlining educational guiding methods, streamlining professional counselling methods, online and mixed counselling, peer training curriculum and training course content design. Another mobility flux, shall take place by the end of the project and, after issuing Romanian course package, it will be implemented for other 20 school counsellors.

Conclusions. Every problematic situation encountered was solved with the close support of the National Agency. The project was a challenge with multiple aspects: participant drop-off, flight cancellation, very reduced budget.

Keywords: Education, Grants, Projects.

Book of abstracts (Personal Development International Conference)

ISSN 2821 – 6474

ISSN-L 2821 – 6474